

人们在测量光速时忽略了光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程，以及基于该过程的重要推论

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摘要：

回顾光速的测量历程、仔细分析光速测量试验可以发现，在测量过程中存在光子的“波函数坍缩和重新生成”的过程，人们没有考虑这个关键性的要点。波函数的坍缩和重建是量子理论中的重要内容，如果考虑了该要点，就一定会发现光速不变还有更加深刻的内涵，这将彻底动摇建立相对论的理论基础。

光子（或电磁波）波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程还是形成粒子的充要条件，也是粒子存在动能、惯性、惯性质量的根本原因。

说明： 后附英语译文。

Note: The English translation is attached below.

一、人们在测量光速时忽略了光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程^①

在光速测量过程中、在测量光子（或电磁波）相对于不同速度参考系的传播速度时，光子（或电磁波）的波函数均存在坍缩和重新生成的过程，这个过程无法回避。所以，我们无法同时测量一个光子相对于两个以不同的相对速度运动的参考系的传播速度。事实上，人们从来没有测量过光相对于不同速度运动的观察者的传播速度。

人们在光速测量过程中忽略了光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程，导致了光速不变假说的建立。

思想试验一：

假设 A 为地面的激光发射器，在垂直方向上距离 A 为 299,792,458 米（1 光秒）处有一个激光接收装置 B。C 为人类制造的反重力装置，C 在其与地球之间的反重力的作用下，能以 0.9 倍光速运动。

在 A、B、C 之间能够以量子纠缠对时的时钟“实时对时”。我们已经知道量子纠缠是超距实时传递的，可以利用多对纠缠粒子使时钟实现实时对时，使对时的准确性不再受光速的限制。……量子计算机已经被人们制造成功，实现这个功能已经不再是问题。

在 C 以 0.9 倍光速离开 A 的同时，A 向 B 发射一份激光 a，C 向 B 直线运动。当 B 接收到 A 发射的激光 a 时，时间间隔为 1 秒。当 C 到达 B 处时，时间间隔为 1.1111...秒。在此期间，我们已经实现了实时对时，不需要考虑任何变换，

不需要计算任何的数据，只考虑平均速度即可。

那么，在这个思想试验中，我们应当认为 a 相对于 C 的传播速度是 $0.1c$ ，而不是 c 。

在 高能粒子对撞机中人们已经测量到高速运动粒子的运动速度。

例如，以 0.9 倍光速运动的高能粒子“跑完同样路程”用了激光的 $1.1111\dots$ 倍时间。该时间差就在那里，但是人们坚持光速不变假设而且用相对论来解释这一切。那么，光速不变假设是正确的吗？

思想试验二：

假设我们在某个比较大的空间范围中拥有了上帝视角，在这个空间范围中我们能够自由的实时感知任意一份光子或电磁波，能够实时分辨所有细节和数据。在这个空间范围中，所有的相对空间体系、所有电磁波、粒子、转换过程，所有一切都一目了然。我们在空间范围 O 中是万能的。

空间范围 O 为真空空间，在 O 中有 A、B、C 三个封闭玻璃箱，均为真空。与空间范围 O 不同，A、B、C 是三个相对空间体系。A 与空间范围 O 相对静止，

图1 关于光速的思想试验

1.1 光子在空间O中传播

1.2 光子波函数在坍塌和重新生成的过程中

1.3 光子跟随所在的相对空间传播

B、C 以相对不同的运动速度相对运动。某时刻，你放出了三个平行运动的全同光子 a、b、c。

下一时刻，光子 a 传播到了 A 的界面，光子 b 传播到了 B 的界面，光子 c 传播到了 C 的界面（图 1，1.1）。

这时你将时间放慢 10^n （倍数大于“ c/λ ”，具体需要多少倍数要以“完全看清光子的转换过程”为准，不要局限于普朗克时间，因为你是万能的）（图 1，1.2）。

这时，仔细分辨三种不同变化：

1. a 从 O 的相对空间转换到 A 的相对空间

因为 A 与 O 相对静止，所以 a 在完全传播进入 A 的过程中没有出现任何变化。

2. b 从 O 的相对空间转换到 B 的相对空间

因为 B 的运动方向与光子传播方向相同，在“b 的前端接触界面开始，b' 传播的同时 B 在运动，到 b'' 完全传播进入 B”

的过程中，b 的波长被拉伸、变大，转换为 b''。在这个过程之内，b 的频率未变化。该过程中光子 b' 的波函数坍缩。

在这个过程中结束后，光子 b'' 跟随 B 传播，光子的波函数重建：

相对于 B，光子 b'' 波长较转换到 B 之前的波长变大，频率变小；

相对于 O，光子 b'' 波长较转换到 B 之前的波长变大，频率不变。

相对于 B，光子在转换的前后频率出现变化的原因是因为 B 的界面在单位时间里经过了较少的光子 b 的波形。而相对于 O，无论 B 扫过了多少波峰和波谷，在 O 的视角中光子的频率不会变化。

3. c 从 O 的相对空间转换到 C 的相对空间

因为 C 的运动方向与光子传播方向相反，在“c 的前端接触界面开始，c' 传播的同时 C 在运动，到 c'' 完全传播进入 C”的过程中，c 的波长被压缩、变小，转换为 c''。在这个过程之内，c 的频率未变化。该过程中光子 c' 的波函数坍缩。

在这个过程中结束后，光子 c'' 跟随 C 传播，光子的波函数重建：

相对于 C，光子 c'' 波长较转换到 C 之前的波长变小，频率变大；

相对于 O，光子 c'' 波长较转换到 C 之前的波长变小，频率不变。

相对于 C，光子在转换的前后频率出现变化的原因是因为 C 的界面在单位时间里经过了较多的光子 c 的波形。而相对于 O，无论 C 扫过了多少波峰和波谷，在 O 的视角中光子的频率不会变化。

4. 人们把上图“1.2 光子波函数在坍缩和重新生成的过程中”这一阶段忽视，直接从图 1 的 1.1 跳到了 1.3，导致了“光速不变”结论。

注：图 1.3 中，a''、b''、c'' 左对齐是为了对比波长，非实际位置。

结论：对比三种不同变化，相对于以不同速度运动的参照系（空间体系），光子的传播速度不同。

这种不同不会导致在不同的参照系里物理量不协变。因为从一个参照系进入另外一个不同速度运动的参照系，光子/电磁波的波函数坍缩和重新生成，重新生成的波函数跟随后一个参照系。

路径返回同理。

光子在前一个参照系和后一个参照系里不是同一个波函数。

我们在不同的参照系的转换过程中，忽略了“1.2 光子波函数在坍缩和重新生成的过程中”，这是在所有的数学公式里永远无法找到的答案。

在思想试验二中，我们可以看到这样的事实：

在光子离开光源、光子被粒子（观察者）接收、光子在不同相对速度运动的粒子（观察者）之间传播、光子传播经过不同介质的界面、光子再发射，光子进

入不同的引力系统的界面，在所有的变化里，光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程无论如何也是不能避免的。

例如，太阳发出的光先是在太阳的引力系统中传播，当传播到地球的引力范围（或进入地球大气层）后，光子波函数经过坍缩和重新生成的过程，重新生成后的波函数跟随地球所在的空间体系，于是我们无论如何测量都是“光速=波长*频率”，我们之所以通过迈克尔逊-莫雷试验得到了光速不变原理，原因在此。人们所以坚持全局光速不变，原因亦在此。……甚至，重新生成的波函数都不需要考虑地球所在的空间体系，因为重新生成的波函数已经跟随了迈克尔逊-莫雷实验装置。更甚至，光子波函数的跟随起始于该实验装置中接触光子的第一个原子。

二、光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程是构成粒子的充要条件

我们都知道奥卡姆剃刀原理，但是真正在建立理论的过程中却完全不是那回事。当年为了解释光速不变假设，增加了“钟慢”、“尺缩”两个实体，在两个实体的引导下又推导出“时空”，而且“可变”。在这几个尺度都可变的时候，一切都能自圆其说，人们在歧途上越走越远。

那么咱们勇敢的举起剃刀，简化再简化：

在思想试验二中，我们把相对运动剃掉，把多余的粒子剃掉，把相对界面剃掉，只剩一个粒子和一份电磁波！

1. 一份电磁波传播进入这个粒子，波函数坍缩和重新生成，重新生成的波函数在粒子内部，相对于粒子所在的相对空间以光速传播。

2. 由于能量辐射，一份电磁波从粒子内部离开时，波函数坍缩和重新生成，重新生成的波函数传播到粒子以外的空间，并以光速传播。

3. 当所有的电磁波都从粒子内部离开，所有电磁波的波函数坍缩和重新生成，电磁波波函数重新生成后在外部空间以光速传播，粒子消失不见。

4. 当该粒子等量的电磁波围住一部分相对空间，这些电磁波的波函数坍缩和重新生成，粒子生成，重新生成的波函数在粒子内部，相对于粒子所在的相对空间以光速传播。

结论：光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程是构成粒子的充分必要条件。

此时，波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程，该过程如此简单却完美，它将成为底层原理。

三、光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程是物质存在动能变化、惯性和惯性质量的根本原因

1. 相对空间、相对空间体系、相对空间转换

与人们对绝对空间与相对空间的定义不同，本文所述的相对空间突出的是空间的相对性。例如可以把每个粒子的空间作为一个相对空间、可以把运动速度相同的物质所在的空间作为一个相对空间，地球也可以作为一个相对空间。

在我们的自然界中相对空间是广泛存在的，只不过人们习惯于称之为参照系。行进中的汽车、火车、轮船，在空气中飞行的飞机，绕地球呈失重状态飞行的卫星、在太空飞行的宇宙飞船，从高空自由落体运动的物体，还有地球、地球的大气层、月球、火星等。所有这些都是相对空间。包括参照系也是相对空间的一种，但是参照系没有考虑光子波函数的坍缩和重新生成，仅仅通过“坐标系变换”考虑了光子的跟随传播。

每个相对空间包含的所有一切，包括其中的电磁波、粒子等物质，运动速度、旋转等属性，可以成为一个相对空间体系。

作者坚持使用相对空间，而不采用参照系的概念，关键因素是光子/电磁波在所有的“不同空间体系的界面之间”进行传播时，均存在波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程。该过程看似简单，却是构成大多数物理现象的前提和基础，作者将其概括为相对空间转换。

这个过程实际是一个思辨性的主题，容易在似是而非的假相中迷惑。我们的物理学体系之所以遇到难以克服的困境，原因就在于这个过程明明是构成各种物理现象的基础性根源，我们忽略了它，远离了真相却试图在迷雾里找到道，不行，而是很容易迷路。

在本书所定义的概念中，“相对空间转换”和“光子/电磁波在不同性质的两个空间体系的界面之间传播时，波函数出现坍缩和重新生成的过程”等价。

两个空间体系的界面可以是粒子与真空之间、粒子与粒子之间、星球之间。例如，在地球与太阳连线之间的引力平衡点附近，靠近地球一侧传播的电磁波与靠近太阳一侧传播的电磁波将会受到不同的引力影响。

2. 运动和动能

以相对空间转换为基础，可以得到运动、动能的本质。

为了更好的探讨运动物体的相对空间转换，我们不能把粒子视为质点，否则我们将永远找不到粒子的真实属性。

如果将粒子视为质点，那么对该粒子的所有作用，包括力的作用，都只能视为通过某种粒子的接触/碰撞来传递。最直观的是人们一直没有发现万有引力与反引力的基础原理，也因此，在量子论基础上发展出量子力学，不能得到基本力的统一描述。

将粒子视为质点可以，但需要知道将其视为质点是将粒子属性进行了简化，以便在某些情景中方便计算，不能将简化情况应用于所有场景——特别是研究粒子属性时。

因为在粒子之间的各种作用中，更广泛存在的是电磁波(光子)的吸收和发射，而吸收的过程在实质上是电磁波成为粒子一部分，发射的过程是电磁波从粒子的一部分被剥离的过程。这个过程是电磁波的波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程，该过程极其细微、极易被人忽略，而忽略该过程就是形成当代物理学迷雾的根本原因。

所以，我们需要将粒子视为具有一定相对空间，在相对空间中包含了粒子所有的电磁波。所有的电磁波均在粒子的相对空间中以光速传播，粒子的内部结构就是粒子在相对运动中所形成的物理特性的基础。在此基础上可以发现运动的本质。

在图 2.1 中，假设粒子 A 相对静止，粒子 B 相对于粒子 A 以速度 v 运动。如果单独拿出任何一个粒子来看，它们没有任何的差别。

图2.1: 相对运动的粒子

但是将两个粒子相对观察、进行碰撞能量的测量时，出现了相对空间的转换，如图，当粒子 B 中的电磁波转换到粒子 A 的相对空间时，在 v 的方向上，电磁波 w_1 的头部离开粒子 B，电磁波的其他部分仍在以 v 向前运动，那么当电磁波全部离开粒子 B 时， w_1' 波长压缩。

在 v 的反方向上：电磁波 w_2 的头部离开 B 时，电磁波的其他部分继续跟随 B 运动，电磁波全部离开粒子 B 时， w_2' 波长被拉伸。

在相对空间转换过程中电磁波的波函数出现了坍塌，并重新生成。

在该过程结束后， W_1' 、 W_2' 相对于 W_1 、 W_2 出现了波长和频率的变化：

$$W_1' \text{ 和 } W_2' \text{ 的波长: } \lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \quad \lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)$$

$$W_1' \text{ 和 } W_2' \text{ 的频率: } \gamma_1 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c-v} \quad \gamma_2 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c+v}$$

粒子 B 相对于粒子 A 的总能量可视为 E_b ，则：

$$E_b = h \cdot \gamma_1 + h \cdot \gamma_2 = h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c-v} + h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c+v}$$

粒子 B 相对于粒子 A，粒子 B 中的电磁波在完成相对空间的转换后，相对于粒子 A 出现了蓝移现象，那么粒子 B 相对于粒子 A，表现出了动能的变化。

当速度 v 接近光速时，粒子 B 相对于粒子 A 的动能将接近无穷大。当然，粒子 A 相对于粒子 B 亦然。这时，粒子 B 与粒子 A 之间将出现高速运动过程中的质能增量。

综上可以推导并得到能量的本质和动能的本质。

能量的本质：某个相对空间体系中的电磁波的总量。

动能的本质：两个相对运动的相对空间体系在发生接触或碰撞时，其中一个空间体系中的电磁波出现相对空间的转换，部分电磁波转移到另外的空间体系中，转移的这一部分电磁波就是动能。转移的过程是相对空间体系对其他相对空间体系做功的过程。

3. 惯性及惯性质量

我们再来看图 2.1：当粒子 B 中的电磁波向粒子 A 的相对空间转换时，出现波长和频率变化的同时，包含的电磁波的能量出现了变化。

粒子的相对空间与其包含的电磁波构成了空间体系，该空间体系的电磁波总体数量及属性的变化不能自行发生。

要使两个粒子趋于一致，必须施加影响，改变其中一方的相对速度（空间属性），而改变其相对速度必然改变其所包含的电磁波的波长和频率，使两者的电磁波的能量趋于一致。改变的过程就是做功的过程。

做功的过程本质上是将一个空间体系中的电磁波向另外一个空间体系转换。如果让粒子 A 达到粒子 B 的状态，需要对粒子 A 施加力的影响，让粒子 A 达到粒子 B 的运动速度。施加的这个力，在粒子 A 中将直接转化为粒子 A 的电磁波，使 A 的电磁波总体数量及属性变化。

如果没有做功的过程，空间体系中的电磁波将不会发生变化，空间体系的空间属性将保持下去。空间体系具有的能够保持自身空间属性的能力就是空间体系的惯性。

空间体系中包含的电磁波数量决定了空间体系阻止空间属性发生改变的能

力值，对外表现就成为了惯性质量。惯性质量的大小取决于空间体系内电磁波的总体数量及属性。

① 该段摘自《光速不变原理中的关键性错误-在测量光速时忽略了光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程-相对论是错误的》，<https://zenodo.org/records/10983315>(论文预印本地址)，作者根据最新研究进行了重新编写。

Note: The English translation is attached below.

The process of photon wave function collapse and regeneration that people ignored this process when measuring the speed of light, and the important inferences based on this process.

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Abstract:

A review of the history of measuring the speed of light and a careful analysis of experiments to measure it reveal that there is a process of "collapse and regeneration of photon wavefunctions" during measurement, which has been overlooked. The collapse and regeneration of wavefunctions are crucial in quantum theory. If this aspect is considered, it becomes evident that the constancy of the speed of light has deeper implications, which could fundamentally shake the theoretical foundation of relativity.

The process of collapse and regeneration of photon (or electromagnetic wave) wavefunctions is also a necessary and sufficient condition for the formation of particles and the fundamental reason for particles to possess kinetic energy, inertia, and inertial mass.

Note: The English translation is attached below.

I. People Ignore the Collapse and Regeneration of Photon Wavefunctions When Measuring the Speed of Light ^①

When measuring the speed of photons (or electromagnetic waves) relative to different reference frames with different velocities, there is an inevitable process of collapse and regeneration of the wavefunctions of photons (or electromagnetic waves). Therefore, it is impossible to simultaneously measure the propagation speed of a photon relative to two reference frames moving at different relative velocities. In fact, people have never measured the speed of light relative to observers moving at different velocities.

Ignoring the collapse and regeneration of photon wavefunctions during the measurement of the speed of light has led to the establishment of the hypothesis of the constancy of the speed of light.

Thought Experiment 1:

Suppose A is a laser emitter on the ground, and B is a laser receiver 299,792,458 meters (1 light-second) away from A in the vertical direction. C is a human-made anti-gravity device that can move at 0.9 times the speed of light due to the anti-gravity force between it and the Earth.

Clocks between A, B, and C can be "synchronized in real-time" using quantum entanglement pairs. We know that quantum entanglement allows for instantaneous transmission over any distance, and multiple entangled particle pairs can be used to synchronize clocks in real-time, making the accuracy of synchronization no longer limited by the speed of light. ... Quantum computers have already been successfully manufactured, so realizing this function is no longer a problem.

As C moves away from A at 0.9 times the speed of light, A emits a laser beam towards B, and C moves in a straight line towards B. When B receives the laser beam emitted by A, the time interval is 1 second. When C reaches B, the time interval is 1.1111... seconds. During this period, we have achieved real-time synchronization and do not need to consider any transformations or calculate any data, only the average speed.

Then, in this thought experiment, we should consider the propagation speed of a relative to C to be $0.1c$, not c .

The speeds of high-energy particles moving at high speeds have been measured in particle accelerators.

For example, high-energy particles moving at 0.9 times the speed of light take 1.1111... times the time of light to "cover the same distance." The time difference is there, but people insist on the hypothesis of the constancy of the speed of light and use relativity to explain everything. So, is the principle of constancy of light velocity, correct?

Thought Experiment 2:

Suppose we have a god's-eye view within a relatively large spatial area, within which we can freely and instantly perceive any photon or electromagnetic wave and instantly distinguish all details and data. Within this spatial area, all relative spatial systems, all electromagnetic waves, particles, and conversion processes are clear briefly. We are omnipotent within the spatial area O.

Spatial area O is a vacuum, and within it are three enclosed glass boxes A, B, and C, all of which are vacuums. Unlike spatial area O, A, B, and C are three relative spatial systems. A is relatively stationary with respect to spatial area O, while B and C move at different relative velocities. At a certain moment, you release three identical photons a, b, and c moving in parallel.

In the next moment, photon a propagates to the interface of A, photon b to the interface of B, and photon c to the interface of C (Figure 1, 1.1).

At this point, you slow down time by 10^n (the multiple is greater than c/λ , and the exact multiple needed depends on "fully seeing the photon conversion process," not limited to Planck time, because you are omnipotent) (Figure 1, 1.2).

At this point, carefully distinguish between three different changes:

1. The transition of a from the relative space of O to the relative space of A

Since A is relatively stationary with respect to O, no changes occur in a as it fully propagates into A.

2. The transition of b from the relative space of O to the relative space of B

Since B moves in the same direction as the photon, within the process which "Starting from the front-end contact interface of b, while b' is propagating, B is in motion, until b" is completely

Figure 1: Thought experiment on the speed of light

1.1 Photons travelling in space O

1.2 Photon wave function in collapse and regeneration

1.3 Photons propagate following the relative space

propagated into B." the wavelength of b is stretched and becomes larger, converting into b". Within this process, the frequency of b does not change. The wavefunction of photon b' collapses during this process.

After this process, photon b" propagates with B, and the photon's wavefunction is reconstructed:

Relative to B, the wavelength of photon b" becomes larger and its frequency smaller than before transitioning into B;

Relative to O, the wavelength of photon b" becomes larger, but its frequency remains unchanged compared to before transitioning into B.

The reason for the change in the frequency of photons before and after their conversion relative to B is that the interface of B passes through fewer waveforms of photons b per unit time. However, relative to O, regardless of how many wave crests and troughs B has scanned, the frequency of the photons does not change from O's perspective.

3. The transition of c from the relative space of O to the relative space of C

Since C moves in the opposite direction to the photon, within the process which "Starting from the front-

end contact interface of c, while c' is propagating, C is in motion, until c" is completely propagated into C." the wavelength of c is compressed and becomes smaller, converting into c". Within this process, the frequency of c does not change. The wavefunction of photon c' collapses during this process.

After this process, photon c" propagates with C, and the photon's wavefunction is reconstructed:

Relative to C, the wavelength of photon c" becomes smaller and its frequency larger than before transitioning into C;

Relative to O, the wavelength of photon c" becomes smaller, but its frequency remains unchanged compared to before transitioning into C.

The reason for the change in the frequency of photons before and after their conversion relative

to C is that the interface of C passes through more waveforms of photons c per unit time. However, relative to O, regardless of how many wave crests and troughs C has scanned, the frequency of the photons does not change from O's perspective.

4. People overlook the stage in the above diagram labeled as "1.2 Photon Wave Function During Collapse and Regeneration Process" and directly jump from 1.1 to 1.3 in Figure 1, leading to the conclusion of "constant speed of light."

Note: In Figure 1.3, the left alignment of a , b , c is for the purpose of comparing wavelengths, not representing their actual positions.

Conclusion: By comparing these three different changes, it is observed that relative to reference frames (spatial systems) moving at different speeds, the propagation speed of photons differs.

This difference does not result in the non-covariance of physical quantities in different reference frames. This is because when a photon/electromagnetic wave enters a different reference frame moving at a different speed from one reference frame, its wave function collapses and regenerates, and the newly generated wave function follows the latter reference frame.

The same principle applies when the path is reversed.

The photon does not have the same wave function in the previous and subsequent reference frames.

In the process of transitioning between different reference frames, we overlook the "1.2 Photon Wave Function During Collapse and Regeneration Process," an answer that can never be found in all mathematical formulas.

In Thought Experiment II, we can observe such a fact:

When a photon leaves its light source, is received by a particle (observer), propagates between particles (observers) moving at different relative speeds, passes through interfaces of different media, is re-emitted, or enters interfaces of different gravitational systems, the process of collapse and regeneration of the photon's wave function cannot be avoided in all these changes.

For instance, light emitted from the sun initially propagates within the gravitational system of the sun. Upon reaching the gravitational sphere of influence of the earth (or entering the earth's atmosphere), the photon's wave function undergoes a process of collapse and regeneration. The newly generated wave function then aligns with the spatial system of the earth. Consequently, regardless of how we measure it, we consistently obtain the equation "speed of light = wavelength * frequency." This is the underlying reason why we derived the principle of the constant speed of light through the Michelson-Morley experiment. It is also the reason why people adhere to the notion of a globally constancy of light velocity. ... Even, there is no need to consider the spatial system of the earth for the newly generated wave function, as it has already aligned with the apparatus of the Michelson-Morley experiment. And even, the to follow of the photon's wave function begins with the first atom in the experimental apparatus that interacts with the photon.

II. The Process of Collapse and Regeneration of Photon Wave Function is a Necessary and Sufficient Condition for Particle Formation

We are all familiar with Occam's Razor principle, but the process of building theories is far from being that straightforward. In the past, to explain the hypothesis of the constant speed of light, two additional entities, "time dilation" and "length contraction," were introduced. These two entities

further led to the derivation of "spacetime," which is also "variable." When these scales are all variable, anything can be justified, and people have gone further and further down the wrong path.

So, let's bravely wield the razor and simplify further:

In Thought Experiment II, we eliminate relative motion, redundant particles, and relative interfaces, leaving only one particle and an electromagnetic wave!

1. When an electromagnetic wave propagates into this particle, its wave function collapses and regenerates. The newly generated wave function is inside the particle and propagates at the speed of light relative to the relative space where the particle is located.

2. Due to energy radiation, when an electromagnetic wave leaves the particle internally, its wave function collapses and regenerates. The newly generated wave function propagates into the space outside the particle and travels at the speed of light.

3. When all electromagnetic waves leave the particle internally, the wave functions of all electromagnetic waves collapse and regenerate. After regeneration, the electromagnetic wave functions propagate at the speed of light in the external space, and the particle disappears.

4. When an equivalent number of electromagnetic waves of the particle surrounds a part of the relative space, the wave functions of these electromagnetic waves collapse and regenerate, leading to the formation of a particle. The newly generated wave functions are inside the particle and propagate at the speed of light relative to the relative space where the particle is located.

Conclusion: The process of collapse and regeneration of photon wave functions is a necessary and sufficient condition for particle formation.

At this point, the process of wave function collapse and regeneration is so simple yet perfect that it will become a fundamental principle.

III. The Process of Collapse and Regeneration of Photon Wave Function is the Fundamental Cause of Kinetic Energy Changes, Inertia, and Inertial Mass in Matter

1. Relative Space, Relative Spatial System, Relative Spatial Transformation

Unlike people's definitions of absolute space and relative space, the relative space discussed in this article emphasizes the relativity of space. For example, the space around each particle can be considered a relative space, the space occupied by matter moving at the same speed can be regarded as a relative space, and the Earth can also be seen as a relative space.

Relative spaces are ubiquitous in our natural world, although people are accustomed to calling them reference frames. Moving cars, trains, ships, airplanes flying in the air, satellites in a state of weightlessness orbiting the Earth, spacecraft traveling in space, objects in free-fall from high altitudes, as well as the Earth, its atmosphere, the Moon, Mars, and so on, are all examples of relative spaces. Reference frames are also a type of relative space, but they fail to consider the collapse and regeneration of photon wave functions, only accounting for the photon's propagation through "coordinate system transformations."

Everything contained within each relative space, including electromagnetic waves, particles, and other matter, as well as properties such as motion speed and rotation, can constitute a relative spatial system.

The author insists on using the term "relative space" rather than the concept of a reference frame. The key factor is that when photons/electromagnetic waves propagate between interfaces of different spatial systems, there is always a process of wave function collapse and regeneration. This

process, though seemingly simple, is the premise and foundation of most physical phenomena and is summarized by the author as "relative spatial transformation."

This process is a dialectical topic and can easily lead to confusion amidst seemingly plausible fallacies. The reason why our physics system encounters insurmountable difficulties is that this process is clearly the foundational source of various physical phenomena, yet we overlook it, straying from the truth while attempting to find the way in the fog. It's not that we can't find it, but it's easy to lose our way.

In the concepts defined in this book, "relative spatial transformation" is equivalent to "the process of wave function collapse and regeneration when photons/electromagnetic waves propagate between interfaces of two spatial systems with different properties."

The interfaces between two spatial systems can be between particles and vacuum, between particles, or between celestial bodies. For example, near the gravitational equilibrium point on the line connecting the Earth and the Sun, electromagnetic waves propagating closer to the Earth's side will be affected differently by gravity compared to those propagating closer to the Sun's side.

2. Motion and Kinetic Energy

Based on relative spatial transformation, we can derive the essence of motion and kinetic energy.

To better explore the relative spatial transformation of moving objects, we cannot treat particles as mere point masses; otherwise, we will never discover their true properties.

Treating particles as point masses implies that all interactions with these particles, including forces, can only be transmitted through some form of particle contact/collision. Most notably, the fundamental principles of gravitational and anti-gravitational forces remain undiscovered, which is why quantum mechanics, developed based on quantum theory, cannot provide a unified description of fundamental forces.

Treating particles as point masses is permissible, but it is crucial to understand that doing so simplifies their properties for convenient calculation in certain scenarios and should not be applied to all situations—especially when studying particle properties.

This is because, among the various interactions between particles, the absorption and emission of electromagnetic waves (photons) are more prevalent. The absorption process essentially involves electromagnetic waves becoming part of the particle, while the emission process involves electromagnetic waves being stripped away from part of the particle. This process involves the collapse and regeneration of the electromagnetic wave function, which is extremely subtle and easy to overlook. Ignoring this process is the root cause of the confusion in contemporary physics.

Therefore, we need to consider particles as possessing a certain relative space that contains all the electromagnetic waves of the particle. All electromagnetic waves propagate at the speed of light within the particle's relative space, and the particle's internal structure forms the basis of the physical properties developed during relative motion. Based on this, we can discover the essence of motion.

In Figure 2.1, let's assume that Particle A is relatively stationary, and Particle B moves at a velocity v relative to Particle A. If we examine either particle individually, there is no discernible difference between them.

Fig.2.1. Particles in relative motion

However, when observing the two particles relatively and measuring their collision energy, a transformation of relative spaces occurs. As illustrated, when the electromagnetic waves in Particle B transition into the relative space of Particle A, in the direction of v , the head of electromagnetic wave w_1 leaves Particle B while the rest of the wave continues to move forward at v . Therefore, when all of electromagnetic wave w_1 has left Particle B, the wavelength of w_1' becomes compressed.

In the opposite direction of v : When the head of electromagnetic wave w_2 leaves Particle B, the rest of the wave continues to move with Particle B. When all of electromagnetic wave w_2 has left Particle B, the wavelength of w_2' becomes stretched.

During the process of relative spatial transformation, the wave function of the electromagnetic waves collapses and regenerates.

After this process ends, changes in wavelength and frequency occur for w_1' and w_2' relative to w_1 and w_2 :

$$\text{The wavelengths of } w_1' \text{ and } w_2': \quad \lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \quad \lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)$$

$$\text{The frequencies of } w_1' \text{ and } w_2': \quad \gamma_1 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c-v} \quad \gamma_2 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c+v}$$

If the total energy of Particle B relative to Particle A is considered as E_b , then:

$$E_b = h \cdot \gamma_1 + h \cdot \gamma_2 = h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c-v} + h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c+v}$$

After completing the relative spatial transformation, the electromagnetic waves in Particle B, relative to Particle A, exhibit a blueshift phenomenon. Therefore, Particle B demonstrates a change in kinetic energy relative to Particle A.

When the velocity v approaches the speed of light, the kinetic energy of Particle B relative to Particle A will approach infinity. Of course, the same applies to Particle A relative to Particle B. At this point, there will be an increase in mass-energy during the high-speed motion between Particle B and Particle A.

In summary, we can derive and obtain the essence of energy and kinetic energy.

The essence of energy: The total amount of electromagnetic waves in a relative spatial system.

The essence of kinetic energy: When two relatively moving relative spatial systems come into contact or collide, the electromagnetic waves in one of the spatial systems undergo a relative spatial

transformation, and part of the electromagnetic waves transfer to the other spatial system. This transferred portion of electromagnetic waves constitutes kinetic energy. The process of transfer is the work done by one relative spatial system on another.

3. Inertia and Inertial Mass

Let's revisit Figure 2.1: When the electromagnetic waves in Particle B undergo a transformation into the relative space of Particle A, changes in wavelength and frequency occur simultaneously, accompanied by changes in the energy of the contained electromagnetic waves.

The relative space of a particle, together with the electromagnetic waves it contains, constitutes a spatial system. Changes in the total quantity and properties of the electromagnetic waves within this spatial system cannot occur spontaneously.

To bring two particles into alignment, an influence must be exerted to alter the relative velocity (spatial property) of one of them. Changing its relative velocity inevitably alters the wavelength and frequency of the electromagnetic waves it contains, causing the energy of the electromagnetic waves of both particles to converge. The process of change is the process of doing work.

The essence of doing work is the transfer of electromagnetic waves from one spatial system to another. To bring Particle A to the state of Particle B, a force must be applied to Particle A to increase its velocity to match that of Particle B. This applied force will directly convert into electromagnetic waves within Particle A, causing changes in the total quantity and properties of its electromagnetic waves.

Without the process of doing work, the electromagnetic waves within the spatial system will remain unchanged, and the spatial properties of the system will persist. The ability of a spatial system to maintain its own spatial properties is inertia.

The number of electromagnetic waves contained within a spatial system determines its ability to resist changes in spatial properties, which manifests externally as inertial mass. The magnitude of inertial mass depends on the total quantity and properties of the electromagnetic waves within the spatial system.

① This paragraph is excerpted from "Crucial Errors in the Principle of the Constant Speed of Light - The Process of Photon Wave Function Collapse and Regeneration Is Ignored When Measuring the Speed of Light - Relativity Is Wrong," with the preprint address at <https://zenodo.org/records/10983315>. The author has rewritten it based on the latest research.